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7 **Phytoplankton growth and microzooplankton**

8 **grazing dynamics across vertical environmental**

9 **gradients determined by transplant in situ**

10 **dilution experiments**

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22

23 **ABSTRACT**

24 The Costa Rica Dome (CRD) represents a paradigmatic case of the bloom-forming capacity of small
25 phytoplankton. Unlike other upwelling systems, autotrophic biomass in the CRD is dominated by
26 picocyanobacteria and small eukaryotes that outcompete larger diatoms and reach extremely high
27 biomass levels. We investigated responses of the subsurface phytoplankton community of the CRD to
28 changes associated with vertical displacement of water masses, coupling in situ transplanted dilution
29 experiments with flow cytometry and epifluorescence microscopy to assess group-specific dynamics.
30 Growth rates of *Synechococcus* (SYN) and photosynthetic picoeukaryotes (PEUK) were positively
31 correlated with light ($R_{\text{pearson_SYN}} = 0.602$ and $R_{\text{pearson_PEUK}} = 0.588$, $p < 0.001$). Growth rates of
32 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), likely affected by photoinhibition, were not light correlated ($R_{\text{pearson_PRO}} =$
33 0.101 , $p = 0.601$). Overall, grazing and growth rates were closely coupled in all picophytoplankton
34 groups ($R_{\text{spearman_PRO}} = 0.572$, $R_{\text{spearman_SYN}} = 0.588$, $R_{\text{spearman_PEUK}} = 0.624$), and net growth rates
35 remained close to zero. Conversely, the abundance and biomass of larger phytoplankton, mainly
36 diatoms, increased more than 10-fold in shallower transplant incubations indicating that, in addition to
37 trace-metal chemistry, light also plays a significant role in controlling microphytoplankton populations
38 in the CRD. Different community dynamics observed in experimental and natural fertilization
39 processes indicate that the ‘sudden’ versus ‘gradual’ pairing of co-limiting light and nutrient
40 availability may be a key to understanding the community response to specific transient physical
41 features.

42

43 INTRODUCTION

44 Picophytoplankton (0.2-2 μm) are commonly viewed as a relatively stable component of the
45 photosynthetic community, while larger phytoplankton cells respond more dynamically to physical
46 perturbations that affect nutrient and light supply (Chisholm, 1992; Marañon *et al.*, 2012). This is the
47 prevailing paradigm for large regions of tropical and subtropical oceans where autotrophic biomass is
48 dominated by picophytoplankton (Li *et al.*, 1983; Letelier *et al.*, 1993), which exhibit little temporal
49 variability despite high turnover rates (Laws *et al.*, 1984; Banse and English, 1994; Gasol *et al.*, 1997).
50 The stability of picophytoplankton standing stocks is to a large extent achieved through protistan
51 grazing activity, which keeps phytoplankton populations in check while efficiently recycling the
52 nutrients that sustain growth of their prey (Landry *et al.*, 1997, 2002; Banse, 2013). Conversely, larger
53 phytoplankton cells, by virtue of their capacity to maintain higher maximum growth rates (Cermeño *et*
54 *al.*, 2005) and their lower susceptibility to grazing (Kiørboe, 1993), dominate in productive systems
55 (Chisholm, 1992; Cullen *et al.*, 2002) and respond to physical perturbations such as mesoscale eddies
56 that inject nutrients into the nutrient impoverished surface waters of tropical and subtropical oceans
57 (Bibby *et al.*, 2008; Brown *et al.*, 2008).

58 The ‘rising tide hypothesis’ provides field evidence that picophytoplankton cellular growth rate
59 and population abundance in the equatorial Pacific respond to the same physical processes that
60 stimulate larger phytoplankton growth (Barber and Hiscock, 2006). Picophytoplankton-dominated
61 blooms reported in oceanic waters of the tropical and subtropical northeast Atlantic (Partensky *et al.*,
62 1996; Gutierrez-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2011) and the Arabian Sea (Latasa and Bidigare, 1998) further
63 support the ability of small phytoplankton to, at least transiently, avoid grazing control and increase
64 their abundance. Given the significant contribution of picophytoplankton to primary production (Li,
65 1994; Agawin *et al.*, 2000; Worden *et al.*, 2004) and the high proportion of this production channeled
66 through protistan grazers (Sherr and Sherr, 2002; Chen *et al.*, 2009), even small perturbations
67 promoting growth and grazing imbalances between these trophic levels can have profound implications
68 for the structure and functioning of pelagic ecosystems. Yet we know very little about the mechanisms
69 that regulate the coupling between phytoplankton growth and microzooplankton grazing, and how
70 these mechanisms interplay with physical and chemical processes to ultimately enhance (or suppress)
71 the accumulation of picophytoplankton biomass under certain environmental conditions (Irigoiien *et al.*,
72 2005).

73 The Costa Rica Dome (CRD) upwelling, an offshore thermal dome that develops seasonally in the
74 eastern tropical Pacific (Fiedler *et al.*, 2006), represents a paradigmatic case of the bloom-forming
75 capacity of small phytoplankton. Unlike other upwelling systems typically dominated by larger
76 eukaryotic phytoplankton (Cullen *et al.*, 2002), the photosynthetic biomass and primary production in
77 the CRD is dominated by picophytoplankton, with *Synechococcus* (SYN) reaching extremely high
78 concentrations (above $\sim 10^6$ cells mL⁻¹) (Li *et al.*, 1983; Saito *et al.*, 2005). Trace-metal availability has
79 been identified as one of the primary factors allowing SYN and *Prochlorococcus* (PRO) to outcompete
80 large eukaryotic plankton in the CRD upwelling system (Franck *et al.*, 2003; Saito *et al.*, 2005; Ahlgren
81 *et al.*, 2014; Chappell *et al.*, this issue). However, in addition to the selective trace-metal conditions for
82 picocyanobacterial growth, the high abundances of SYN, PRO and photosynthetic picoeukaryotes
83 (PEUK) during the CRD summer upwelling suggest unusual mechanisms that allow small
84 phytoplankton to escape the tight grazing control typically exerted by microzooplankton. In order to
85 gain insights into how top-down processes contribute to the establishment of the distinctive
86 phytoplankton community structure of the CRD, and more generally into the conditions that favor the
87 accumulation of picophytoplankton, we conducted transplant dilution experiments during the upwelling
88 season of the CRD. We investigated how changes in environmental conditions associated with the
89 onset of the summer upwelling affected phytoplankton growth and grazing mortality dynamics. We
90 prepared a series of replicated dilution experiments with subsurface water collected from a single
91 depth, which were subsequently incubated in situ across eight different depths spanning the euphotic
92 zone. We analyzed the variability of SYN, PRO and PEUK growth and grazing rates, and daily
93 changes of microphytoplankton biomass when incubated at different irradiance levels. We
94 hypothesized the following: 1) that the growth of phytoplankton community exposed to higher
95 irradiance would be enhanced relative to grazing, leading to positive phytoplankton net growth rates,
96 while the opposite would be expected when the community is switched to lower irradiance conditions
97 at deeper layers; 2) that SYN would maintain higher growth rates than PRO when transplanted to high
98 illuminated surface layers, while the latter would maintain higher net growth rates when transplanted to
99 deeper layers; and 3) that diatoms would be favored over picophytoplankton when transplanted to
100 shallower waters by virtue of their fast-growth capacity and lower susceptibility to protistan grazing.

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103 **METHODS**

104 **Study area, hydrography and sample collection**

105 We sampled the CRD upwelling region (Fig. 1) on R/V *Melville* cruise MV1008 (22 June - 25 July,
106 2010) as part of the CRD FLUX and Zinc Experiments (FLUZIE) cruise, which had the broad goals of
107 characterizing plankton community structure, biogeochemical fluxes and mechanisms of phytoplankton
108 control in this ecosystem. Sampling and experiments were conducted in 3-4 day periods of activity,
109 called ‘cycles’, during which the water parcel tracked by drift array was followed and sampled daily
110 (Landry *et al.*, 2009). Hydrographic data (temperature, salinity, fluorescence and dissolved oxygen)
111 and discrete water samples were acquired with a CTD-rosette system with 24 10-L Niskin bottles with
112 Teflon-coated springs. Seawater samples were collected from 8 depths in the upper 80-120 m at each
113 station, extending from the surface to the depth of penetration of ~0.1% surface irradiance (E_0). Each
114 depth was sampled for macronutrients, chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*), flow cytometry (FCM), and analysis of
115 microplankton by digitally enhanced epifluorescence microscopy (Taylor *et al.*, 2011, this issue).
116 Nutrient samples were filtered directly from the Niskin bottle through an acid-washed, seawater-rinsed
117 0.1 μm Suporcap filter capsule to 45 mL plastic tubes and stored frozen at -18°C until analysis. The
118 tubes were rinsed twice, filled, immediately frozen (-20°C), and later analyzed for major nutrient
119 concentrations ($\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$, NO_2^- , PO_4^{3-} , NH_4^+ , and SiOH_3) by flow injection by the Analytical
120 Laboratory at the Marine Science Institute, University of California, Santa Barbara using standard wet-
121 chemistry methods (Gordon *et al.*, 1992). Samples (250 mL) for Chl *a* were immediately filtered onto
122 25 mm GF/F filters, and the pigment was extracted with 90% acetone in a dark freezer (-20°C) for 24 h
123 and quantified on a calibrated Turner Designs model 10 fluorometer (Landry *et al.*, 2009). For FCM
124 analysis, 2 mL seawater samples were preserved with 0.5% paraformaldehyde (final concentration)
125 (Sigma Aldrich), flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and transferred to a -80°C freezer until analysis. For
126 microscopical assessment of nano- and microplankton, aliquots of 250 mL were collected, preserved,
127 and then stained with proflavin (0.33 w/v) allowing them to fix for at least one hour before filtering
128 onto 8.0- μm and staining with DAPI (Taylor *et al.*, 2011).

129 **Pico-phytoplankton analysis by flow cytometry**

130 Cell abundances of SYN, PRO and PEUK were measured using a Becton-Dickinson FACSort
131 flow cytometer equipped with a 488-nm argon laser following the procedure described in Collier and
132 Palenik (Collier and Palenik, 2003). Prior to analysis, fixed samples were thawed and kept in the
133 dark at room temperature for less than an hour, and a known concentration of standard beads (0.97

134 μm , Green Fluorescent, Duke Scientific) was added to each sample for fluorescence normalization.
135 SYN, PRO, and PEUK populations were distinguished based on their Chl *a* (red fluorescence, 680
136 nm), phycoerythrin (orange fluorescence, 564-606 nm), forward-angle (FALS) and 90° light side-
137 scatter (SSC) signatures. Cell counts were converted into cell concentrations (cells mL^{-1}) by
138 calculating the volume injected for each sample from the weight of the sample tube measured before
139 and after each run. PRO and SYN cell abundances were converted into carbon using 32 and 101 fg
140 C cell⁻¹, respectively (Garrison *et al.*, 2000; Brown *et al.*, 2008), adjusted for biovolume changes
141 with depth using bead-normalized FALS^{0.55} as scaling factor (Binder *et al.*, 1996; Landry *et al.*,
142 2003). To convert PEUK cell abundances to carbon biomass, we used the total PEUK biomass and
143 cell abundances estimated by Taylor *et al.* (Taylor *et al.*, this issue) to calculate the mean biomass for
144 PEUK cells in each cycle with such data available (Cycle 2=156 fg C cell⁻¹, Cycle 3=149 fg C cell⁻¹,
145 and Cycle 4= 267 fg C cell⁻¹), and the mean cell biomass calculated from all other cycles in Cycle 5
146 (Cycle 5=185 fg C cell⁻¹).

147 **In situ incubation experimental design**

148 We conducted a series of transplant dilution experiments at four different locations in the CRD
149 region corresponding to the last day of experimental Cycles 2 to 5. At each station, seawater
150 collected from the subsurface chlorophyll maximum (~20-30 m, 10% E₀) was used to prepare eight
151 replicated two-treatment dilution assays (Landry *et al.*, 1984; 2008). For each dilution assay, one
152 0.26-L polystyrene tissue culture container was filled with whole seawater (WSW), and a second
153 bottle was filled with 0.2 L of 0.1- μm filtered seawater (FSW) before filling it to the top with WSW.
154 Replicated dilution assays were then incubated for 24 h at different depths attached to a drifting array
155 with a surface float and a mixed-layer drogue at 15 m (Landry *et al.*, 2009). This set up allowed us
156 to expose replicates of the microbial community sampled from a single depth to a gradient of in situ
157 irradiance and temperature conditions across the euphotic zone. Flow cytometry samples were taken
158 at time zero from the collection depth and after 24 h from each experimental incubation and depth.
159 These abundance estimates were used to calculate the net rates of change (*k*) of SYN, PRO and
160 PEUK. Instantaneous growth (μ , d⁻¹) and grazing (*m*, d⁻¹) rates for each group were estimated
161 assuming that grazing mortality declines linearly with dilution, as confirmed by full dilution
162 experiments (Selph *et al.*, this issue). Accordingly, the net rate of change (*k*) of cell abundance is $k =$
163 $\mu - m$ in the undiluted bottles and $k_d = \mu - x_m$ in diluted bottles, where “*x*” is the fraction of natural
164 grazer density in the dilute treatment (0.24 in these experiments). The two equations, $m = (k_d - k) /$
165 $(1 - 0.24)$ and $\mu = k + m$, were then solved for the two unknowns, μ and *m*.

166 **Microscopical assessment of nano- and microplankton**

167 Seawater samples (250 mL) for nano- and microplankton abundance and biomass assessment were
168 processed and analyzed using digital epifluorescence microscopy as described in Taylor *et al.* (Taylor
169 *et al.*, this issue). Briefly, slides were imaged and digitized with a Zeiss AxioVert 200M inverted
170 epifluorescence microscope equipped with a fully motorized stage and controlled by Zeiss AxioVision
171 software. Slides were viewed at 200X, and at least 20 random fields per slide were imaged. Each field
172 image consisted of three- to four different fluorescent channels: Chl *a*, DAPI, FITC and phycoerythrin.
173 The separate channel images for each field were composited into 24-bit RGB images for analysis.
174 Counting and sizing of eukaryotes >8 μm cell lengths was semi-automated with ImagePro software.
175 Cells were identified and grouped manually into three functional groups (diatoms, autotrophic
176 flagellates and autotrophic dinoflagellates). All cells were binned into 5-10, 10-20, 20-40 and >40- μm
177 based on measurements of the longest cells axis. Length (L) and width (W) measurements were
178 converted to biovolumes (BV; μm^3) by applying the geometric formula of a prolate sphere ($\text{BV}=0.524$
179 LWH), assuming the unmeasured cell height (H) equals cell width ($\text{H}=\text{W}$). Carbon biomass (pg C cell⁻¹)
180 was computed: $\text{C}=0.215 \times \text{BV}^{0.939}$ for non-diatoms, and $\text{C}=0.288 \times \text{BV}^{0.811}$ for diatoms (Mender-
181 Deuer and Lessard, 2000).

182 **Statistical analysis**

183 Statistical analyses were conducted on experimental results using GraphPad 5.0 software.

184 **RESULTS**

185 **Hydrography, nutrients, and Chlorophyll *a***

186 The surface mixed layer was markedly shallow for Cycles 2 and 4 (10-15 m) located inside the
187 dome and extended deeper for Cycles 3 and 5 (25-30 m) located outside of the dome (Fig. 2A).
188 Surface temperature was similar for all experiments (27.6 ± 0.53 °C, mean \pm SD) and decreased
189 dramatically down to ~ 16 °C by ~ 40 m, which gave a sharp temperature gradient in the euphotic zone
190 (Fig. 2A). Surface salinity was virtually identical in all profiles (33.50 ± 0.01), but a steep halocline
191 reached asymptotic values at shallower depths than the thermocline (20-30 m), particularly in Cycles 2
192 and 4 (Fig. 2A). The resulting strong pycnocline separated two water masses with distinctive physical,
193 chemical and biological characteristics within the euphotic zone. Chl *a* concentration in surface waters
194 ranged from 0.25 to 0.30 mg m^{-3} , increased to subsurface maxima at 20-30 m depth (~ 0.4 mg m^{-3}) and

195 decreased rapidly ($< 0.1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) below 40 m. However, the chlorophyll maximum in Cycle 5 was less
196 conspicuous, with relatively higher values ($\sim 0.2 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) down to 70 m (Fig. 2A).

197 Figure 2B shows the vertical distributions of picophytoplankton populations in the water samples
198 used to prepare the transplant experiments (Fig. 2B). More detailed descriptions of the structure and
199 dynamics of picophytoplankton populations across the CRD are presented elsewhere (Selph *et al.*, this
200 issue; Taylor *et al.*, this issue). Maximum concentrations of SYN were high in the surface mixed layer
201 and decreased abruptly below the pycnocline, particularly in Cycles 3 and 5 (Fig. 2B; Taylor *et al.* this
202 issue). In addition to lower surface concentrations, SYN was virtually absent below the mixed layer at
203 these stations (Fig. 2B). Conversely, SYN concentrations below the mixed layer remained substantial
204 in Cycles 2 and 4, and showed a secondary peak ($\sim 10^5 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B), which in some cases
205 reached higher abundances than at the surface (Taylor *et al.*, this issue). PRO vertical distributions also
206 differed between Cycles 2 and 4 and Cycles 3 and 5 located inside and outside of the dome,
207 respectively (Fig. 2B). In Cycles 2 and 4, PRO abundances peaked in subsurface waters ($\sim 40 \text{ m}$, $1\text{-}3 \times$
208 $10^5 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$), while they were highest in the surface mixed layer in Cycle 3 and 5 ($0.2\text{-}0.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cells}$
209 mL^{-1}) and decayed rapidly below the pycnocline (Fig. 2B). PEUK concentrations in the surface mixed
210 layer were similar in Cycles 2, 3 and 4 ($2 \text{ to } 2.5 \times 10^4 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$), each showing a subsurface peak that
211 reached concentrations up to $4.0 \times 10^4 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$ just below the pycnocline (Fig. 2B). In Cycle 5,
212 PEUK abundance was lower ($\sim 1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$) but represented a larger proportion of the total
213 picophytoplankton community (Fig. 2B).

214 **Pico-phytoplankton growth, grazing and net growth rates**

215 Growth and grazing rates estimated for subsurface populations SYN, PRO and PEUK incubated
216 across the water column are summarized in Table 1 and graphically represented in Figure 3. Intrinsic
217 growth rates estimated from incubations conducted at the same depth of sample collection were higher
218 in Cycles 2 and 5 than in Cycles 3 and 4 for all groups (Table 1, Fig. 3). Overall, PEUK showed higher
219 growth rates ($\mu = 0.90 \pm 0.38 \text{ d}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD, $n=4$) than SYN ($\mu = 0.57 \pm 0.22 \text{ d}^{-1}$), and PRO ($\mu = 0.58$
220 $\pm 0.19 \text{ d}^{-1}$) ($F = 8.45$, $p = 0.018$, repeated measures ANOVA). Grazing rates were similar or higher
221 than growth rates in all cycles, except for Cycle 5, where growth exceeded grazing (Table 1, Fig. 3).
222 Mean group-specific grazing rates mirrored those for growth, with PEUK showing higher values ($m =$
223 $0.87 \pm 0.49 \text{ d}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD, $n = 4$) than SYN ($m = 0.61 \pm 0.25 \text{ d}^{-1}$) and PRO ($m = 0.58 \pm 0.19 \text{ d}^{-1}$),
224 although the differences were not significant in this case ($F = 2.24$, $p = 0.18$, repeated measures

225 ANOVA). Net growth rates at the depth of sample collection were slightly negative for SYN and PRO
226 while the opposite was true for PEUK (Table 1, Fig. 3).

227 Growth rates of picophytoplankton groups decreased gradually when transplanted to deeper waters
228 with lower irradiance levels (Fig. 3). This trend was consistent among all groups and experiments,
229 although the decay was more pronounced in Cycles 2 and 5 (Fig. 3). In these cycles, growth rates
230 measured at $\sim 5\% E_0$ were ca. 5-fold lower than those at the sample collection depth ($\sim 10\% E_0$) for all
231 picophytoplankton groups, with SYN showing the strongest decrease (Table 1, Fig. 3). Grazing rates
232 for all picophytoplankton groups decreased with decreasing irradiance levels as well, although the
233 minimum values in the lower euphotic zone differed among cycles. While grazing rates at irradiance
234 levels $\leq 1\% E_0$ were virtually zero in Cycles 3 and 5, they remained substantial ($\sim 0.25 \text{ d}^{-1}$) for Cycles 2
235 and 4 (Table 1 and Fig. 3), which may indicate differences in the protistan grazing impact on primary
236 production and nutrient recycling at the lowest light levels of the euphotic zone. When transplanted to
237 shallower depths, the picophytoplankton community response was more variable among cycles and
238 populations (Fig. 3). For Cycles 2 and 4, all populations had lower growth rates when transplanted to
239 the surface mixed layer while the opposite response was observed in Cycle 3 (Fig. 3). In Cycle 5
240 experiments, however, cell growth of SYN and PEUK remained constant or increased slightly in the
241 vicinity of the collection depth and sharply decreased at the shallowest incubation depth, whereas PRO
242 showed decreasing growth rates in all incubations above the sample collection depth (Fig. 3). Mean
243 growth rates estimated across transplanted depths were significantly higher for PEUK ($0.29 \pm 0.38 \text{ d}^{-1}$,
244 mean \pm SD) and SYN ($0.24 \pm 0.34 \text{ d}^{-1}$) compared to PRO ($0.09 \pm 0.27 \text{ d}^{-1}$) (Table 1, $F = 4.65$, $p =$
245 0.014 , repeated measures ANOVA), although the 75th percentile of PEUK growth rate ($\mu_{75\text{th_percentil}} =$
246 0.48 d^{-1} , $n = 25$) was about two fold higher than that for SYN and PRO ($\mu_{75\text{th}} = 0.28$, and 0.25 ,
247 respectively).

248 Grazing rates displayed similar vertical trends to phytoplankton growth, and both process rates
249 were strongly correlated either within each experiment (Fig. 4) or combining the data from all
250 experiments in all groups ($R_{\text{spearman_PRO}} = 0.572$, $R_{\text{spearman_SYN}} = 0.588$, $R_{\text{spearman_PEUK}} = 0.624$). The
251 slopes and Y-intercepts of grazing and growth model II regressions were not significantly different
252 from 1 and 0, respectively (Fig. 5), suggesting an overall balance between both rates across all
253 incubations. As a consequence of this close coupling, net growth rates remained close to zero,
254 although the occasional imbalance between growth and grazing led to substantial net growth rates,
255 mainly for the shallowest incubations (Fig. 3 and 5). In Cycle 5, for instance, the enhanced growth
256 rates of SYN and PEUK at higher irradiance levels were not matched by grazing and yielded positive

257 net growth rates, while for Cycle 4 we observed the inverse situation in which the opposing trends of
258 growth and grazing rates yielded net consumption (Fig. 3). In contrast to growth, mean grazing rate for
259 PRO ($0.28 \pm 0.08 \text{ d}^{-1}$) was not significantly different than for PEUK ($0.36 \pm 0.08 \text{ d}^{-1}$) and SYN ($0.27 \pm$
260 0.09 d^{-1}) ($F = 1.04, p = 0.35$, repeated measures ANOVA), which further reflects the growth and
261 grazing imbalance of PRO in the surface transplant experiments (Fig. 3).

262 **Pico-phytoplankton growth and grazing relationships with light and temperature**

263 The effects of light and temperature on picophytoplankton growth, grazing and net growth rates
264 were explored by simple linear regression analysis (Fig. 6, Table II). Growth rates of SYN and PEUK
265 were positively correlated with irradiance levels ($\log \%E_0$) ($R_{\text{pearson_SYN}} = 0.602$ and $R_{\text{pearson_PEUK}} =$
266 $0.588, p < 0.001$) while significant correlation was absent for PRO ($R_{\text{pearson_PRO}} = 0.101, p = 0.601$; Fig.
267 6, Table II). This was also true for the ambient community (Selph *et al.*, this issue). Growth and
268 grazing rates of SYN and PEUK were also positively correlated with the temperature change,
269 expressed as the difference between ambient temperature at incubation and at collection depth ($T' - T_0$)
270 ($R_{\text{pearson_SYN}} = 0.602$ and $R_{\text{pearson_PEUK}} = 0.588, p < 0.001$), but this was not the case for PRO ($R_{\text{pearson_PRO}}$
271 $= 0.04, p = 0.84$). Conversely, grazing mortality for PRO was positively correlated with irradiance
272 ($R_{\text{pearson_PRO}} = 0.528, p < 0.01$), underlying the decreasing net growth observed with increasing
273 irradiance ($R_{\text{pearson_PRO}} = -0.503, p < 0.01$) (Fig. 6). Grazing rates of SYN and PEUK were positively
274 correlated with irradiance levels and yielded regression parameters (Table II) not significantly different
275 from the growth-irradiance relationships (ANCOVA, $p > 0.2$). On the other hand, net growth rates of
276 SYN and PEUK varied closely around zero despite dramatic changes in ambient irradiance and
277 temperature during the transplanted incubations, yielding insignificant relationships with irradiance and
278 temperature (Table II, Fig. 6).

279 **Nano- and micro-phytoplankton net growth dynamics**

280 The biomass of larger phytoplankton ($>8 \mu\text{m}$) increased in shallower incubations, although
281 responses to the incubation conditions differed among functional groups (Fig. 7A). Autotrophic
282 dinoflagellates for instance, seemed to do best when incubated at the depth of collection, while
283 transplants to different light and temperature decreased their growth (Fig. 7A). Conversely, net
284 accumulations of autotrophic flagellates and especially diatoms were favored by conditions prevailing
285 in shallower water incubations (Fig. 7A). This trend was consistent among all cycles, and shifted the
286 community structure of surface incubations towards higher contributions of larger phytoplankton (Fig.

287 8). Maximum biomass levels in transplant incubations were observed in experiments conducted
288 outside the dome (Cycles 3 and 5, Fig. 7A), particularly in Cycle 5 where diatoms took over the
289 community at the shallowest incubation depth. In experiments conducted within the dome (Cycles 2
290 and 4), the accumulation of diatoms was less marked, although the modest increase of larger
291 phytoplankton observed in Cycle 4 (Fig. 7A) was clearly reflected in community structure after 24 h of
292 incubation due to strong photoinhibition of picophytoplankton in shallow waters.

293 A closer look into the size structure of diatoms in three size fractions (10-20, 20-40 and >40- μm)
294 showed that the intermediate fraction had the highest abundance in surface incubations (Fig. 7B).
295 However, the >40- μm diatom fraction contributed most to biomass accumulation (Fig. 7C).
296 Normalization of the diatom biomass in transplanted incubations relative to collection depth
297 incubations showed that the stimulation of net growth rate was strongest, in relative terms, for Cycles 2
298 and 5 (9-fold). Biomass of the 20-40 μm size fraction often showed a disproportionate response of up
299 to a 25-fold increase (Fig. 7D), a somehow counterintuitive result given the dominant contribution of
300 the larger fraction to total diatom biomass.

301 **DISCUSSION**

302 **Experimental approach and potential artifacts**

303 The objective of this study was to analyze the variability of phytoplankton community growth and
304 grazing dynamics in response to irradiance changes associated with the CRD upwelling. In an attempt
305 to simulate physico-chemical changes experienced by the phytoplankton and microzooplankton
306 community during the seasonal shoaling and mixing of thermocline waters, we transplanted the
307 microbial community from the subsurface chlorophyll maximum to shallower and deeper layers, and
308 estimated the daily rates of growth, grazing and net accumulation of major phytoplankton groups from
309 in situ dilution assays. Simulation of in situ light exposure of natural plankton communities during
310 incubation experiments is always challenging, and photoacclimation-related artefacts can quickly arise
311 (Gutiérrez-Rodríguez and Latasa, 2011). This study circumvents at least some of these problems by
312 using a pseudo-lagrangian drift array (Landry *et al.*, 2009) that allowed us to incubate simultaneously
313 eight replicated dilution assays across a gradient of irradiance conditions spanning the euphotic zone.
314 Despite the methodological and biological variability expected from manipulated and non-replicated
315 experiments, the process rates estimated along the water column were consistent within each cycle
316 experiment (Fig. 3) and with growth and grazing rates estimated independently at the collection depths
317 (Landry *et al.*, this issue; Selph *et al.*, this issue).

318 To avoid complications inherent to pigment-based rate estimates, we assessed population
319 dynamics from changes in cell abundance and biomass measured by flow cytometry and
320 epifluorescence microscopy. Mimicking natural light exposure accurately is particularly important for
321 incubations with light-limited phytoplankton, because, in addition to changes in cellular pigment
322 content that arise from mismatches of ‘natural’ and ‘experimental’ irradiance conditions,
323 photosynthetic rates will be sensitive to small differences in light exposure. In this sense, the highly
324 stratified waters and vertically structured phytoplankton community of the CRD upwelling region
325 (Gutiérrez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2014, Fig. 2) provide a relatively stable gradient of depth-dependent light
326 exposures, at least compared to regions with deeper mixed layers, that minimizes photoacclimation
327 issues associated with fixed-depth incubations. Indeed, vertical profiles of fluorescence per cell
328 volume quantified by flow cytometry (FL3/SSC) (Fig. 9) indicate that picophytoplankton cells adjusted
329 their pigment contents to changes in light exposure during the 24-h transplant incubations. Cell
330 pigment contents decreased in samples transplanted to shallow depths, remained relatively constant in
331 samples incubated at the depth of collection, and remained relatively constant or decreased in deeper
332 water incubations (Fig. 9). These changes are largely consistent with the physiological responses
333 expected for acclimation of light-limited phytoplankton transferred to increasing photon flux density
334 dose. The lack of cell pigment increase in deeper incubations can reflect a reduced physiological status
335 of the phytoplankton populations, which seemed to have a lesser effect on PRO than SYN populations
336 (Fig. 9) with deeper and shallower distribution, respectively (Fig. 2). Overall, the photoacclimation
337 dynamics described supports the validity of the experimental design to investigate phytoplankton
338 population dynamics under a realistic range of physiological conditions.

339 **Pico-phytoplankton growth and grazing response to environmental gradients**

340 We hypothesized that growth rates of phytoplankton transplanted to shallower waters would be
341 enhanced by favorable light conditions that allowed the community to fully exploit the higher nutrient
342 concentrations carried upward from subsurface waters. The significant positive linear relationship
343 between growth rate and irradiance observed for SYN and PEUK (Fig. 6, Table II) is consistent with
344 this hypothesis. The absence of such relationship for PRO is mainly due to high-light depression of
345 growth rate observed at shallow depths (Fig. 3). This trend has been previously observed from both
346 HPLC and FCM-based growth rate estimates in the equatorial Pacific (Selph *et al.*, 2011) and is also
347 consistent with the higher cell death observed for PRO compared to SYN and PEUK at high irradiance
348 levels (Llabrés and Agustí, 2006). A more detailed look into the vertical profiles of phytoplankton
349 growth indicates that, despite the statistical significance of the positive growth-irradiance relationship

350 observed for SYN and PEUK, their responses to higher light in shallower waters varied among
351 experiments (Fig. 3). Given that increasing temperature can inactivate proteins and affect the cell
352 division capacity (Ratkowsky *et al.*, 1983), one can speculate that the variable response in shallow
353 incubations relates to the magnitude of the temperature difference between collection and mixed layer
354 depths (MLD), which could explain the steeper high-light depression observed in Cycles 2 and 4
355 ($\Delta T_{z_{MLD}-z_0} \sim 10$ °C) compared to Cycle 3 ($\Delta T_{z_{MLD}-z_0} \sim 3$ °C). However, the persistence of this decaying
356 trend across the mixed layer ($\Delta T < 0.125$ °C) (e.g. Cycle 4) and the higher sensitivity of PRO to
357 increasing irradiance compared to SYN and PEUK (Fig. 3, 9) (Partensky *et al.*, 1999; Llabrés and
358 Agustí, 2006; Scanlan *et al.*, 2009), points toward excess light as the likely cause for the lack of
359 systematic growth stimulation in shallower incubations (Fig. 4).

360 In addition to enhancing phytoplankton growth through photosynthesis, light can also stimulate
361 digestion, grazing and growth of phagotrophic protists feeding on pigmented prey (Strom 2001). In our
362 dataset, grazing rates on all picophytoplankton groups were significantly and positively related to
363 irradiance (Fig. 6), supporting the hypothesized effect of light on community grazing. Although the
364 initial and 24-h final samplings of our experiments preclude evaluation of day-night rhythms in
365 grazing, the positive relationship between grazing and light levels is in agreement with the higher
366 protistan grazing activity during the day compared to night reported in experiments conducted with
367 natural (Kuipers and Witte, 2000; Dolan and Simek, 1999) and cultured grazer populations (Jakobsen
368 and Strom, 2004). On the other hand, the decreasing grazing mortality observed in deeper incubations
369 seems consistent with the systematic lower grazing mortality estimated from dilution experiments
370 incubated at lower light conditions (Gutiérrez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009). In contrast with these
371 observations, a recent mesocosm experiment conducted in eastern Mediterranean oligotrophic waters
372 failed to detect systematically enhanced microzooplankton grazing in high light (60% E_0) compared to
373 low light conditions (6% E_0) (Calbet *et al.*, 2012), suggesting that other factors such as trophic structure
374 and interactions (e.g., mixotrophy) could affect the light dependence of grazing.

375 Based on the primary need of light for phytoplankton photosynthesis, we hypothesized that growth
376 would decrease faster than grazing rate when samples were transplanted to deeper waters, leading to a
377 parallel decrease in net growth rates. For SYN, the slope and the Y-intercept of the grazing linear
378 regressions on irradiance were higher (Table II, Fig. 6), indicating that grazing remained substantial
379 when phytoplankton growth became light limited and implying that a larger proportion of primary
380 production was consumed by protistan grazing at lower light levels. This trend is consistent with
381 reports of decoupled phytoplankton growth and microzooplankton grazing in natural communities

382 under relatively low irradiance conditions manipulated in the lab (Gutiérrez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009) or
383 in the deeper euphotic zone of the equatorial Pacific (Landry *et al.*, 2011). In the case of PEUK, the
384 slopes of growth and grazing rates as a function of irradiance were virtually identical, suggesting that
385 both process rates decay in a similar way with light. Furthermore, net growth rates did not significantly
386 increase with irradiance (Fig. 6), although photoinhibition in surface incubations (Fig. 3 and 9) was
387 largely driving this trend, particularly in the decreasing net growth rates observed for surface PRO (Fig.
388 6). Despite the lack of mixing in fixed-depth bottle incubations, which can increase the total light
389 exposure and exacerbate the photoinhibition response of phytoplankton in shallow waters, the extended
390 use of UV-opaque containers in seawater dilution and primary production assays counteracts this effect
391 to some extent by relieving the experimental populations from the UV-derived oxidative stress
392 affecting natural populations (Llabrés and Agusti, 2006; Beardall *et al.*, 2009; Llabrés *et al.*, 2010;
393 2011). Data on deleterious effects of high irradiance on grazers are scarce (Sommaruga *et al.*, 1996;
394 Ochs and Eddy, 1998); however, one can speculate on the lesser effects that light-derived oxidative
395 stress may have on non-photosynthetic (*i.e.*, non-pigmented) grazers, or conversely, the potential
396 benefits from light-aided digestion, as mechanisms that explain why grazing tends to remain similar or
397 increase while growth is photoinhibited (Fig. 3). Regardless of the mechanisms, these results suggest
398 that in addition to low-light conditions in the deep euphotic zone, the higher-light conditions of shallow
399 waters can tilt the balance between picophytoplankton growth and mortality in ways that enhance the
400 proportion of primary production consumed by protistan grazers.

401 **Close coupling between growth and grazing**

402 In our data set, growth and grazing rates are strongly correlated both within experiments (Fig. 4)
403 and picophytoplankton group, indicating that they remained tightly coupled along the gradient of
404 conditions explored (Table 1) despite large variability in process rates (Fig. 4). Growth and grazing
405 rates estimated from independent dilution experiments are often positively correlated, with
406 phytoplankton groups showing higher growth rates being usually consumed at higher rates as well
407 (Burkill *et al.*, 1987; Strom *et al.*, 1991; Latasa *et al.*, 2005). The lack of independence between
408 growth and grazing in the ecological model assumed by the dilution method can contribute to this
409 correlation (Gutiérrez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009). In our dataset, however, the growth and grazing
410 correlations associated with this methodological issue ($R_{\text{spearman_methodological}} = 0.12 \pm 0.19$, 0.18 ± 0.18 ,
411 and 0.10 ± 0.19 for PRO, SYN, and PEUK, respectively) were significantly lower than the correlations
412 observed ($R_{\text{spearman_PRO}} = 0.572$, $R_{\text{spearman_SYN}} = 0.588$, $R_{\text{spearman_PEUK}} = 0.624$). The strong ecological link
413 between growth and grazing rates suggested by these results is consistent with the close coupling

414 observed between picophytoplankton growth and mortality rates (Chen *et al.*, 2009; Cáceres *et al.*,
415 2013), and further highlights the highly dynamic nature of this coupling (Strom 2002). In this sense,
416 despite the significant relationship between grazing and irradiance ($r^2 \sim 0.3$, Fig. 6), it is worth noting
417 that growth rate itself remains the best predictor of grazing rates for picophytoplankton ($r^2 \sim 0.5$, Fig. 4
418 and 5).

419 The high correlation between growth and grazing rates makes it difficult to distinguish between the
420 direct (e.g., ‘light-aided’ digestion) and indirect effects that light may exert on grazing rates through
421 internal regulation (i.e., higher grazing on faster growing prey). In experiments where the processes
422 are clearly decoupled due to photoinhibition of phytoplankton growth, grazing tends to increase with
423 increasing irradiance, particularly for PRO (e.g., Cycle 4, Fig. 4), supporting a direct link between light
424 and community grazing. Laboratory experiments performed with *Oxyrrhis marina* and *Dunaliella*
425 *tertiolecta* growing on a 2-stage chemostat system, have shown significantly higher prey content and
426 slower vacuole evacuation rates in cultures maintained in the dark compared to light (Décima and
427 Gutiérrez-Rodríguez, unpublished data), suggesting a direct effect of light upon digestion. Taken
428 together, these laboratory and field results support the role of light not only as a resource for
429 phytoplankton growth but also as an important factor modulating grazing mortality dynamics.
430 Regardless of the mechanism, the rapid response of protistan grazers to sudden environmental
431 perturbations affecting picophytoplankton growth highlights the resilience of this trophic coupling and
432 its role in stabilizing planktonic ecosystems.

433 **Nano- and microphytoplankton net growth response and community structure**

434 The scarcity of larger cells, particularly in the diluted treatment, precludes robust determination of
435 microphytoplankton growth rates from standard microscopy counts. Yet, comparisons of cell
436 abundance and biomass in the non-diluted incubations across the different incubation depths allow us
437 to assess net responses of the microphytoplankton community to irradiance changes associated with the
438 transplant incubations. These results show an accumulation of larger phytoplankton, mainly diatoms,
439 at shallower incubation depths (Fig. 7 and 8), in agreement with the capacity of diatoms to respond
440 quickly to sudden increase of resource supply (Sarhou *et al.*, 2005). Given that nutrient concentrations
441 were the same across all replicated incubations (*i.e.*, the same water sample), the rapid accumulation of
442 diatoms in high-light transplanted incubations suggest suboptimal light conditions for diatom growth in
443 the deeper waters. Only after exposure to higher irradiance levels could diatoms fully exploit their
444 physiological and maximum growth capacities (Furnas *et al.*, 1990; Cermeño *et al.*, 2005), producing a
445 major shift in community structure in shallow incubations after only 24 h (Fig. 8). A growing body of

446 evidence suggests that the unusual community structure of the CRD upwelling results from the unique
447 trace-metal conditions of the region (Franck *et al.*, 2003; Saito *et al.*, 2005; Chappell *et al.*, this issue),
448 including higher cobalt concentrations and metal complexation (Ahlgren *et al.*, 2014). Nonetheless, the
449 proliferation of diatoms in well-lit shallow transplant incubations compared to those kept at low-light
450 deeper waters, having both the same initial nutrient availability (Fig. 7), suggests that light availability,
451 in addition to trace-metal chemistry, plays a significant role in modulating phytoplankton growth and
452 community structure in the CRD.

453 Culture experiments have shown an increase in cellular iron requirement for phytoplankton under
454 low-light conditions, allowing for simultaneous limitation of phytoplankton growth by iron and light
455 (Sunda and Huntsman, 1997; 2011). In natural systems iron and light co-limitation has been described
456 for surface phytoplankton populations in the Southern Ocean and high-latitude Pacific Ocean with
457 mixed layers extending beyond the euphotic zone (Boyd *et al.*, 1999; Mitchell *et al.*, 1991; Smith *et al.*,
458 2000), as well as for subsurface populations forming the deep chlorophyll maximum over a wide region
459 of the Pacific (Hopkinson and Barbeau, 2008; Johnson *et al.*, 2010). Using microcosm manipulation
460 experiments Hopkinson and Barbeau (Hopkinson and Barbeau, 2008) observed that the response of
461 diatoms to iron enrichment was strongest under high-light conditions, while iron addition at ambient
462 low-light levels was often not sufficient to trigger significant changes in phytoplankton biomass and
463 composition. Similarly, Johnson *et al.* (Johnson *et al.*, 2010) found a positive and comparable response
464 of diatoms to both '+light' and '+light+iron' treatments in grow-out experiments conducted with
465 natural phytoplankton assemblages sampled from the DCM at several locations across the equatorial
466 and subtropical Pacific. The accumulation of diatoms in high-light transplant incubations is consistent
467 with these experimental observations and further supports the central role of light in determining the
468 dynamics and composition of subsurface populations in well-stratified systems.

469 In addition to the nutrient fertilization of shallower waters, the doming of the isopycnals that defines
470 the CRD upwelling can potentially represent a light-enriching mechanism (*sensu* Diehl *et al.*, 2002).
471 Yet, the diatom accumulation generally observed in our light-enriched incubations is at odds with the
472 picophytoplankton-dominated community that develops in the CRD where diatoms remain rare
473 members despite the upwelling nature of the system (Li *et al.*, 1983; Saito *et al.*, 2005; Taylor *et al.*,
474 this issue). Results of extensive studies on phytoplankton control mechanisms in the eastern equatorial
475 Pacific (EEP) may help to reconcile these differences between experimental and in situ observations.
476 The EEP is a high-nutrient low-chlorophyll area where low levels of iron prevent the growth of larger
477 diatoms (Coale *et al.*, 1996a; Landry *et al.*, 1997). A recent comprehensive survey of phytoplankton

478 structure and dynamics across the iron limited EEP showed that iron supply associated to the westward
479 shoaling of the pycnocline stimulated *Prochlorococcus* rather than diatom biomass (Selph *et al.*, 2011).
480 This result contrasts with the diatom-dominated community response in bottle and in situ mesoscale
481 experiments in this (Martin *et al.*, 1991; Chavez *et al.*, 1991; Coale *et al.*, 1996a, b) and other putative
482 iron-limited oceanic regions such as the subarctic Pacific (DiTullio *et al.*, 1991; Welschmeyer *et al.*,
483 1991) and the Southern ocean (Boyd *et al.*, 2007; Smetacek *et al.*, 2012). Selph *et al.* (Selph *et al.*,
484 2011) argued that the low-light conditions prevented diatoms from utilizing new nutrients entering the
485 lower-euphotic zone, which were instead consumed by small phytoplankton before they reached the
486 well-lit shallower waters. Similarly, our transplant experimental design implies a different resource-
487 supply scenario for phytoplankton in which relatively nutrient-rich subsurface waters are suddenly
488 exposed to high-light conditions where diatoms can fully exploit their high nutrient uptake and fast
489 growth capacity before small picophytoplankton exhaust the limiting nutrient. These results support
490 the inability of diatoms to compete with picophytoplankton for the limiting nutrient (i.e., cobalt or zinc)
491 under low light conditions, and stress the importance that resource supply mechanics associated with
492 different fertilization mechanisms may have on the community response.

493 Mesoscale and sub-mesoscale physical features such as fronts, eddies and internal waves are
494 known to affect the growth environment for phytoplankton as well as and system trophic status
495 (Benitez-Nelson and McGilicuddy, 2008). Our results show that protistan grazing may also respond to
496 light changes caused by vertical displacements of isotherms associated with such physical events,
497 influencing the fate of the primary production stimulated by the same process. These experiments
498 provide further evidence of the robustness and highly dynamic nature of the close coupling between
499 picophytoplankton growth and grazing dynamics, which remained tight despite perturbation along
500 strong environmental gradients. In addition, accumulation of larger phytoplankton, and particularly
501 diatoms, was systematically enhanced in well-lit shallow incubations illustrating the light-limited
502 conditions of subsurface populations and the capacity of larger cells to bloom when that limitation is
503 lifted suddenly. Nonetheless, the surface phytoplankton community that develops naturally in response
504 to summer upwelling conditions of the CRD is dominated by small phytoplankton. The different
505 community responses to manipulative experiments compared to natural fertilization processes, suggest
506 that the ‘sudden’ versus ‘gradual’ pairing of resource availability (i.e., light and nutrient) may be a key
507 factor influencing changes in the size and taxonomic structure of the phytoplankton community that
508 can develop in response to transient physical features.

509

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519

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714 **TABLE LEGENDS**

715 Table I. Picophytoplankton growth (μ), grazing (m) and net growth (μ_{net}) rate estimates for the
716 transplant experiments conducted at different depths in all cycles. Optical depth ($\%E_0$) and
717 temperature (T) for each incubation are also given. Categories are: *Synechococcus* (SYN),
718 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), and picoeukaryotes (PEUK). Units are percentage of incident irradiance for
719 optical depth, temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and growth, grazing and net growth rates (d^{-1}). Data from the sample
720 collection depth are in bold.

721 Table II. Results of simple linear regression analysis on the growth, grazing and net growth rate
722 estimates for *Synechococcus* (SYN), *Prochlorococcus* (PRO) and picoeukaryotes (PEUK) using the
723 percentage of incident irradiance ($\%E_0$) as independent variable. Irradiance data were \log_{10}
724 transformed prior to analysis. Error represents the standard error of the mean (SEM, $n = 30$).

725 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

726 Fig. 1. Map of the Costa Rica Dome area showing the stations occupied daily during each of the
727 experimental cycles. Stations where transplant experiments were carried out are indicated on the map
728 as C2, C3, C4 and C5.

729 Fig. 2. Vertical profiles of physico-chemical (A) and biological (B) properties at the beginning of
730 transplant experiments conducted during each cycle. Fluorescence (FL), chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*),
731 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), *Synechococcus* (SYN), picoeukaryotes (PEUK)

732 Fig. 3. Rates of growth, grazing and net growth of PRO, SYN, and PEUK populations in transplant
733 incubations conducted at different irradiance levels expressed as a function of percent surface
734 irradiance in the water column. Dashed horizontal line indicates the depth where the sample water
735 used for the preparation of the eight replicated dilution experiments was collected. Solid vertical line is
736 located at zero rate values for reference.

737 Fig. 4. Bivariable plot of grazing mortality and growth rates for each of the transplant experiment for
738 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), *Synechococcus* (SYN), and picoeukaryotes (PEUK). Spearman correlation
739 coefficient (R) estimated for each group is indicated within each plot. Dashed lines represent the 1:1
740 relationships.

741 Fig 5. Model II linear regressions between grazing mortality and growth rates estimated for
742 *Synechococcus* (SYN), *Prochlorococcus* (PRO) and picoeukaryotes (PEUK) across all transplant
743 experiments (dashed line). Regression parameters are estimated excluding shallowest incubations
744 (Solid line, cross-filled symbol). Error bars are standard errors of the mean.

745 Fig. 6. Simple linear regressions of growth (solid circles), grazing (empty circles) and net growth
746 (triangles) rates against incubation irradiance levels ($\log \%E_0$) estimated for *Synechococcus*,
747 *Prochlorococcus*, and picoeukaryotes. The slope (\pm standard error of the mean) of the regression and
748 the correlation coefficient are shown.

749 Fig. 7. Phytoplankton carbon biomass ($\mu\text{g C L}^{-1}$) and cell abundance at the end of the incubations in
750 the non-diluted treatment (A, B, C) and relative change in carbon biomass between sample incubation
751 and collection depths (D). Diatoms, autotrophic flagellates (AF), autotrophic dinoflagellates (ADinos).

752 Fig 8. Relative contribution of major phytoplankton groups to total autotrophic community carbon
753 biomass in the non-diluted treatment at the end of the incubations. *Synechococcus* (SYN),
754 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), picoeukaryotes (PEUK), diatoms, autotrophic flagellates (AF), autotrophic
755 dinoflagellates (ADinos). Arrows indicate the original depth of sample collection.

756 Fig. 9. Vertical profiles of the ratios between red fluorescence per side scatter (FL3/SSC) at the sample
757 collection and incubation depths at the end of the experiment shown as an index of strength of
758 photoacclimation occurring during the 24-h transplant incubations.

759 Table I. Picophytoplankton growth (μ), grazing (m) and net growth (μ_{net}) rate estimates for the transplant experiments conducted at different
760 depths in all cycles. Optical depth (%E₀) and temperature (T) for each incubation are also given. Categories are: *Synechococcus* (SYN),
761 *Prochlorococcus* (PRO), and picoeukaryotes (PEUK). Units are percentage of incident irradiance for optical depth, °C for temperature and
762 d⁻¹ for growth, grazing and net growth rates. Data from the sample collection depth are in bold.

Cycle	Depth (m)	Optical depth (%E ₀)	T (C)	SYN			PRO			PEUK		
				μ (d ⁻¹)	m (d ⁻¹)	μ_{net} (d ⁻¹)	m (d ⁻¹)	μ (d ⁻¹)	μ_{net} (d ⁻¹)	μ (d ⁻¹)	m (d ⁻¹)	μ_{net} (d ⁻¹)
Cycle 2	2	85.9	27.8	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Cycle 2	12	40.1	27.6	0.14	0.45	-0.31	-0.02	0.40	-0.43	0.19	0.65	-0.46
Cycle 2	20	21.8	20.5	0.19	0.20	-0.01	-0.17	-0.08	-0.09	0.08	0.20	-0.12
Cycle 2	30	10.2	17.2	0.83	0.97	-0.14	0.68	0.84	-0.16	1.28	1.52	-0.24
Cycle 2	40	4.8	16.0	0.10	0.41	-0.31	0.17	0.55	-0.38	0.11	0.60	-0.49
Cycle 2	50	2.2	14.8	-0.12	0.12	-0.24	-0.12	0.14	-0.26	-0.20	0.18	-0.38
Cycle 2	60	1.0	14.2	-0.18	0.11	-0.29	-0.14	0.15	-0.29	-0.28	-0.04	-0.25
Cycle 2	80	0.2	13.5	-0.02	0.34	-0.36	0.04	0.42	-0.38	-0.07	0.32	-0.39
Cycle 3	2	89.4	28.3	1.27	2.31	-1.05	0.53	1.69	-1.16	1.17	1.30	-0.13
Cycle 3	12	50.9	27.9	0.24	-0.50	0.74	0.70	0.75	-0.05	1.02	1.32	-0.29
Cycle 3	20	32.5	26.0	0.40	0.59	-0.19	0.43	0.44	-0.01	0.70	0.60	0.10
Cycle 3	30	18.5	19.1	0.04	0.21	-0.17	0.19	0.29	-0.11	0.18	0.22	-0.04
Cycle 3	45	8.0	15.5	0.08	0.13	-0.06	0.16	0.24	-0.09	0.15	0.13	0.02
Cycle 3	60	3.4	14.6	0.27	0.31	-0.05	0.33	0.45	-0.12	0.36	0.17	0.19
Cycle 3	80	1.1	13.9	-0.11	-0.16	0.05	-0.06	-0.10	0.03	0.04	-0.12	0.15
Cycle 3	100	0.4	13.3	0.05	-0.04	0.09	0.02	-0.10	0.12	0.44	0.16	0.28
Cycle 4	2	86.3	27.2	-2.44	0.93	-3.37	-2.34	0.79	-3.14	-0.38	0.40	-0.78
Cycle 4	12	41.3	26.5	0.28	0.48	-0.20	-0.28	0.46	-0.74	0.09	0.44	-0.35
Cycle 4	20	22.9	19.5	0.28	0.35	-0.07	0.13	0.26	-0.13	0.72	0.65	0.07
Cycle 4	30	11.0	16.3	0.38	0.47	-0.09	0.43	0.58	-0.15	0.47	0.40	0.07
Cycle 4	40	5.3	14.7	0.20	0.20	0.00	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Cycle 4	50	2.5	14.4	0.21	0.04	0.17	0.18	0.05	0.12	0.31	0.18	0.13
Cycle 4	60	1.2	13.9	0.28	0.27	0.02	0.34	0.33	0.01	0.32	0.36	-0.05
Cycle 4	80	0.3	13.5	0.13	0.23	-0.10	0.11	0.22	-0.11	0.00	0.19	-0.19
Cycle 5	2	88.5	27.7	0.67	-0.08	0.75	-0.68	-0.24	-0.44	0.86	0.31	0.55
Cycle 5	12	48.0	27.7	0.87	0.47	0.39	-0.02	0.57	-0.59	0.52	0.02	0.50
Cycle 5	20	29.4	27.1	0.83	0.52	0.31	0.25	0.56	-0.31	0.84	0.78	0.07
Cycle 5	30	16.0	19.8	0.68	0.42	0.26	0.80	0.45	0.35	1.14	0.96	0.18
Cycle 5	40	8.7	17.5	0.26	0.44	-0.18	0.38	0.28	0.10	0.36	0.65	-0.29
Cycle 5	50	4.7	16.2	0.11	0.01	0.09	0.26	0.13	0.13	0.23	0.70	-0.48
Cycle 5	70	1.4	14.6	0.17	0.10	0.08	-0.10	-0.27	0.17	-0.20	-0.22	0.02
Cycle 5	100	0.2	14.1	0.00	-0.06	0.05	0.07	-0.12	0.19	0.08	-0.03	0.11

763 Table II. Results of simple linear regression analysis on the growth, grazing and net growth rate
 764 estimates for *Synechococcus* (SYN), *Prochlorococcus* (PRO) and picoeukaryotes (PEUK) using the
 765 percentage of incident irradiance (%E₀) as independent variable. Irradiance data were log₁₀
 766 transformed prior to analysis. Error represents the standard error of the mean (SEM, *n* = 30).

Phytoplankton group	Dependent variable	Independent variable	Slope ± SEM	Y-Intercept ± SEM	r ²	p-value
<i>Synechococcus</i>	μ	%E ₀	0.27 ± 0.06	0.070 ± 0.069	0.4073	0.0001
	m		0.22 ± 0.10	0.13 ± 0.12	0.1366	0.0444
	μ _{net}		0.05 ± 0.08	-0.069 ± 0.09	0.0143	0.5366
<i>Prochlorococcus</i>	μ	%E ₀	0.048 ± 0.07	0.12 ± 0.08	0.0147	0.5304
	m		0.23 ± 0.08	0.14 ± 0.09	0.218	0.0107
	μ _{net}		-0.18 ± 0.07	-0.02 ± 0.07	0.207	0.0131
Picoeukaryotes	μ	%E ₀	0.33 ± 0.08	0.11 ± 0.09	0.3671	0.0005
	m		0.29 ± 0.09	0.20 ± 0.10	0.2833	0.003
	μ _{net}		0.038 ± 0.07	-0.090 ± 0.074	0.01233	0.5663

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770 **Figure 1**

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773 **Figure 2**

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776 **Figure 3**

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779 **Figure 4**

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782 **Figure 5**

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Prochlorococcus

Synechococcus

Picoeukaryotes

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785 **Figure 6**

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787 **Figure 7**

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790 **Figure 8**

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793 **Figure 9**